

SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF TYPHOID FEVER AMONG CHILDREN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Typhoid fever continues to be a major public health problem. Effective control of the disease would benefit from an understanding of the subnational geospatial distribution of the disease incidence. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates the global burden of typhoid fever at 11–20 million cases per year, resulting in 140,000 deaths. Transmission usually occurs via the fecal-oral route, typically when an individual ingests contaminated food or water. Of S. Typhi.

Objective: To highlight the Social Determinants of Typhoid Fever among Children.

Methodology: A Cross sectional study design was used at MNCH Nawabshah, SBA. The total of 350 n patients were selected through the manual sample size formula, non-probability convenient sampling strategy was applied. Mothers of cases/ children aged between 0 to 12 years with typhoid fever having positive test (Typhidot) or Blood Culture either getting treatment or newly diagnosed cases confirmed through laboratory report and treatment or follow up were included and Non -consenting mothers or guardians has been excluded. Data related to role of the social determinants of typhoid fever was collected through structured questionnaire. Confidentiality of the participant's information was ensured during data collection, analysis and interpretation.

Results: The mean age 6.79 with ± 2.924 standard deviation, 201 (57%) Male & 149 (43%), Single type of family 74%, with lower class 69% they lived in 47.10% kacha. child bath 70% daily, dirty 38% nails, service latrine 59%, pit latrine 26%, 58% used only toilet, 42% field, bore water 75%, packed juice 89%, dairy milk 84%.

Conclusion: The Determinants of typhoid fever were highly related with the spreading and prognosis of disease, it was highly concluded that sanitation and improvement of personal hygiene were decrease the burden of typhoid fever among children. The findings of the study revealed that there is dire need of initiating the interventions for promoting the health education programs and specific intervention strategies among the children, in the light of sustainable Development goals and WHO WASH Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Typhoid fever continues to be a major public health problem. Effective control of the disease would benefit from an understanding of the subnational geospatial distribution of the disease incidence. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates the global burden of typhoid fever at 11–20 million cases per year, resulting in 140,000 deaths¹. Transmission usually occurs via the fecal-oral route, typically when an individual ingests contaminated food or water. *S. Typhi* characteristically invades the gastrointestinal tract and progresses to systemic infection². The risk of infection has previously been linked to factors such as exposure to contaminated water, inadequate waste management, poor hygiene conditions as well as inhabitation of urban slums³.

The disease can result to major complications such as internal hemorrhage and perforation. In the absence of effective treatment, this disease has a fatality rate of about 10 to 30 %⁴. The incidence of typhoid fever is 100–1,000 cases per 100,000 population in the developing world⁵.

A study was conducted in India shows that the estimated incidence of typhoid fever from hospital surveillance ranged from 12 to 1622 cases per 100,000 child-years among children between the ages of 6 months and 14 years and from 108 to 970 cases per 100,000 person-years among those who were 15 years of age or older⁶. Typhoid attack rate in the cohort was 0.9%, with the highest attack rate of 1.7% being documented in one of the four areas. The rate of hospitalization and complications in children who were typhoid positive during the outbreak was 28% and 2%, respectively⁷.

Another study was conducted at sub-Saharan Africa revealed that the incidence rates ranged from 43.7 (95% confidence interval: 0.6 to 591.2) in Zimbabwe to 2,957.8 (95% CI: 20.8 to 4,245.2) in South Sudan per 100,000 person-years⁸. Population-based studies under the Diseases of the Most Impoverished project in urban slums of Pakistan and India estimated the blood culture-proven typhoid incidence between 184.9 and 493.5 cases per 100,000 person years, respectively, among 5- to 15-year-old children⁹.

Prevention of typhoid fever is essential to reduce mortality, with the ultimate goal of a comprehensive approach that utilizes

vaccination, improvements in water, sanitation, and hygiene, and greater access to surgical care¹⁰. Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) are critical for human health. Despite this, over 884 million people worldwide lack access to safe drinking water. Almost 2.4 billion people do not have access to even the most basic sanitary facilities. Many people practice open defecation, endangering the safety of drinking water and personal water supplies¹¹. One of the study was conducted in china shows that the countries affected by typhoid and paratyphoid fever, 10,000–18,000 typhoid/paratyphoid cases being reported each year in China. Zhejiang Province was one of the typhoid/paratyphoid fever high-risk areas in China, with an incidence of 1.1 per 1,000,000 in 2013¹².

This study will highlight the social determinants of the typhoid fever in which main emphasis placed on the uncovered street foods served with poor hygienic practices to children. Drinking unsafe water or use of bore water remained a major risk factor for the typhoid fever. Once the determinants will be uncovered through this study then the preventive measures will be addressed on the basis of this study findings. So this study will provide the baseline data for the most emerging social determinants of typhoid fever.

MATERIAL & METHODS

The Cross sectional study design was used. This study was carried out from 1st April to 31st December 2019 at Pediatric department including ward and outpatient department of MNCH Nawabshah, SBA. The total of 350 n patients were selected through the manual sample size formula, the study subjects were all the patient of typhoid fever who have confirmed by Blood test for the typhoid fever whether a typhi dot or the blood culture tests. This study was approved by the Ethical Review Committee of the People's University of Medical Health Sciences for Women Nawabshah (Shaheed Benazir Abad), Pakistan. Permission was taken from Head/ Chairman of Department of Paeds and informed written consent was taken from Respondents. Confidentiality of the participant's information was ensured during data collection, analysis and interpretation and non-probability convenient sampling was used with following sample selection criteria.

Children with age of 0-12 years with confirm blood culture and positive test (Typhidot) came for follow-up were included and non-consenting children or guardians were excluded. Data related to Social determinants of typhoid fever was collected through structured questionnaire. Questionnaire was self- designed through the literature review and expert’s opinions then also the Cronbach’s alpha was applied to test the reliability and validity of the developed tool. The result showed value of Cronbach’s alpha .087 a highly reliable tool. Questions were asked about demographic data and social determinants with using Likert scale and dichotomous. Data was analyzed by statistical package for social sciences version (SPSS) 25.0. Confounding will be controlled by Stratification. Data was presented by Tables, Graphs, Charts, Diagrams and Histograms.

RESULTS

A total of 350 children patients were included in this study after fulfill inclusion and exclusion criteria with mean age 6.79 with ± 2.924 standard deviation (Figure 1) 46% 4-7 years of

age & 30% 8-12 years 24% 1-3 Years of age and their mothers are 97% house wives (Figure 2). The majority of patients were 201 (57%) Male & 149 (43%) Female (Figure 3), the mostly related to Single type of family 74%, joint 23% and extended 3% (Figure 4)with lower class 69%, middle class 22% and upper class 9% of socioeconomic status (Figure 5). They lived in 47.10% kacha, 37.40% pacca and 15.40 semi pacca type of houses (Figure 6).

The results of study showed that (Table 1) child bath 70% daily, 30% alternate, clean 62%, dirty 38% nails, service latrine 59%, pit latrine 26%, 58% used only toilet, 42% field for other places for defecation. 40% preserved food in refrigerator, 3% drying, 32% eat junk food. The main source of water results showed that bore water 75% pipe water 9% filter plant water 15% and bottled water 1%. Fresh juice 11% packed juice 89%, dairy milk 84%, packed milk 3%, 47% boiled, and 37% not boiled the dairy milk. 89% always discard the tea or milk or food after flies dropped in it, home protection from flies 95% No, 82% were not in contact of any other typhoid patient.

Figure 1: Age of children

Figure 2: Mother's Occupation

Figure 3: Gender

Figure 4: type of Family

Figure 5: Socioeconomic Status

Figure 6: type of Houses

Table 1: Social Determinants of typhoid fever

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	
Child Bath	Daily 242 (70%)	Alternate 108 (30%)
Nails	Clean 216 (62%)	Dirty 133 (38%)
Latrine at Home	Yes 294 (84%)	No 56 (14%)
Type of Latrine	Service Latrine 205 (59%)	Pit Latrine 89 (26%) Other 56 (15%)
Use of Other places for defecation	I only use latrine or toilet 202 (58%)	Field 148 (42%)
Preserve foods	Yes 154 (44%)	No 196 (56%)
If Yes: How you preserve foods	Refrigerator 141(40.3%)	Drying 13 (3.7%)
Eat raw Vegetables or fruits at Home	Yes 232 (66%)	No 118 (34%)
Food eaten outside Home	Yes 166 (47%)	No 184 (53%)
If Yes: Types of Food	Junk 113 (32%)	Curry 15 (4%) Bar, BQ 38 (11%)
Main source of Water at home	Bore water 263(75%)	Pipe Water 30 (9%) Filter plant 51 (15%) Bottled 6 (1%)
Drinking boiled Water	Always 10 (3%)	Sometime 37 (11%) Never 303 (86%)
Type of Ice you use	Locally Purchase 196 (56%)	Home Made 154 (44%)
Type of Juices you take	Fresh Juice 40 (11%)	Packed Juice 310 (89%)
Source of Milk	Dairy 293 (84%)	Packed 11(3%) NA 46 (13%)
If Tick Dairy: Take boiled Dairy Milk	Yes 165 (47%)	No 128 (37%)
Discard your tea / milk or Food if you noticed flies dropped in it	Always 311(89%)	Often 2 (1%) Sometime 27 (8%) Never 10(2%)
Eating sweets even you noticed flies were on it	Always 10 (3%)	Sometime 41 (12%) Never 299 (85%)
Eating meals remained uncovered	Always 12 (3%)	Often 5 (1%) Sometime 59 (17%) Never 274(79%)
Home protected with net for flies	Yes 16 (5%)	No 334 (95%)
Contact with another typhoid patient	Yes 19 (5%)	No 286 (82%) I Don't Know 45 (13%)

DISCUSSION

This study included 350 child patients out of which 201 (57%) male & 149 (43%) were females (Figure 3). The mean age 6.79 with \pm 2.924 standard deviation (Figure 1) 46% 4-7 years of age & 30% 8-12 years 24% 1-3 Years of age. Same like a study was conducted during May-October 2018 in Karachi, the capital city of Sindh Province in Pakistan revealed that 0-4 years 27 (36%), 5-9 Years 34 (45%) and 10-14 Years 14 (19%)¹³, most of the participants were belongs to single type of family 74% (Figure 4) with lower socioeconomic (69%) (Figure 5) with 47% kacha type of houses (Figure 6). The majority of mothers were house wives 97% (Figure 2) compare to study was conducted Combined Military Hospital Peshawar which 51(51.5%) were male and 48 (48.4%) were females, socioeconomic status below average 47 (47.4%) average 37 (37.3%) and above average 15 (15.1%)¹⁴.

The study also emphasizes the dealing with the Social determinants or modifiable risk factors which along with burden of disease help in the major aspect of this disease as, 66% had consumed raw food, 37% had history of unpasteurized dairy milk consumption, 86% had not drinking boiled water, and 47% had consumed outside food and drinks 32% junk food^{15,16,13,17}. Which was parallel with the study done by Raza J Et al which showed increase contamination by salmonella bacterium in ready to eat foods.

These risk factors that were highlighted were like the study conducted by Brockett S Et al which showed that modifying these risk factors significantly prevented the disease and every risk factor has a significant percentage attributable to the disease and is preventable with some direct or indirect intervention^{4,18,19}.

CONCLUSION

The typhoid fever is the considerable problem of Pakistan especially in the children although the epidemiological data is limited to estimate the prevalence and major risk factors among children in Pakistan. The social determinants which are highlighted in the study included raw food, unpasteurized milk, and socioeconomic status, clean water, outside food, and type of latrine or defecation, uncovered food and type of houses with specific protection from flies.

Which again emphasizes that educating the masses can decrease the national burden of disease significantly.

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